

Studies in the Cycloheptane Series. Part V. Synthesis of Some Derivatives of α -Arylamino-cycloheptane

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Cycloheptanone has been condensed with a number of arylamines and aqueous potassium cyanide in presence of acetic acid to furnish α -arylamino-cycloheptane-1-cyanides. The latter have been converted to their respective amides. Only two of these amides have been used for preparation of the corresponding acids and carbinols.

Interest in the chemistry of indoxyl spiro-cycloalkanes was first aroused by the discovery of indoxyl spiro-cyclopentane (II), obtained by heating the acetyl derivative of dihydroxyhexahydrocarbazole¹ (I) with sulphuric acid and acetic anhydride. The structure of this product, as suggested by Robinson², could be (II) or (III) and on theoretical consideration, the former was preferred. Sidgwick and Plant³ found that indoxyl spiro-cyclopentane (II) formed a salt with alkali metals and considered it to be a complex. In view of this property and to confirm the structure of the dehydration product (II), obtained from (I), Plant and Facer⁴ took up its synthesis. They prepared 1-anilino-cyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (Vd) according to the method of Tiemann⁵ and subjected it to alkaline fusion to obtain (II). Bucherer and Grolee⁶ had earlier prepared an analogous compound, 2,2-dimethylindoxyl (VII) by alkaline fusion of (VI).

- V a: $n = 2$; $R = \text{CN}$; $R_1 = \text{OH}$. V f: $n = 4$; $R = -\text{COOH}$; $R_1 = -\text{NHPh}$.
 b: $n = 2$; $R = \text{CN}$; $R_1 = -\text{NHPh}$. g: $n = 4$; $R = \text{CN}$; $R_1 = -\text{NHAr}$.
 c: $n = 2$; $R = -\text{CONH}_2$; $R_1 = -\text{NHPh}$. h: $n = 3$; $R = \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$; $R_1 = -\text{NHPh}$.
 d: $n = 2$; $R = -\text{COOH}$; $R_1 = -\text{NHPh}$. i: $n = 4$; $R = \text{CH}_2\text{OH}$; $R_1 = -\text{NHPh}$.
 e: $n = 3$; $R = -\text{COOH}$; $R_1 = -\text{NHPh}$.

1. Perkin and Plant, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 676.

2. Private communication with the above workers (see reference 1).

3. *Ibid.*, 1925, 200.

4. *Ibid.*, p. 2037.

5. *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2039.

6. *Ber.*, 1903, 39, 986.

Preparation of 1-anilino-cyclopentane-1-cyanide (Vb) from the ketone (IV) *via* the cyanohydrin (Va), the amide (Vc), and the acid (Vd) were carried out smoothly, but the alkaline fusion of this acid afforded the carbazole (VIII) instead of the product (II). This behaviour of the cyclopentane derivative as against the synthesis of (VII) was considered extraordinary, but no satisfactory explanation was offered by these workers.

This failure in the synthesis of (II) brought in a new interest in the chemistry of indoxyl spiro-cycloalkanes about the part played by the cycloalkane ring during this cyclisation. Betts *et al.*⁷ were, however, able to synthesise indoxyl spiro-cyclohexane (IX) by reactions similar to those adopted by Bacher⁸ and Groloc⁶.

Buksh *et al.*⁸ by carrying out a similar series of reactions from a completely different point of view concluded that the cyclohexano ring did not exhibit boat-chair isomerism⁹. With β -decalone, however, Desai *et al.*¹⁰ were able to confirm the presence of the two ring isomers required by Hückel's theory¹¹ for these rings.

Recently, a new interest has developed in the chemistry of these anilino compounds as these seem to be useful starting materials for the syntheses of certain cycloalkylene nitriles and carboxylic acids which find important use in polymerisation reactions and preparation of some of these have even been patented¹²⁻¹⁴. These unsaturated compounds, especially the carboxylic acids, can be easily obtained by pyrolysis of the anilino compounds. This tendency was first noticed by Betts *et al.*⁷ and later studied by Bain and Ritchie¹⁵ who also compared the pyrolysis of the derivatives of cyclopentane (Vd), cyclohexane (Ve), and cycloheptane (Vf) and came to the conclusion that the ring size was important in the formation of cycloalkylene carboxylic acids. Thus, under strictly standard conditions, the relative amounts of (Xa, b, and c) from the corresponding anilino-acids varied with the ring size and were found maximum with the cycloheptane derivative.

With this enhanced importance, the synthesis of the cycloheptane analogues was taken up. 1-Arylamino-cycloheptane-1-cyanides (Vg) were prepared according to the method of Walther and Hubner¹⁶. Hydrolysis of the nitriles to the respective amides was effected by the method of Buksh *et al.*⁸, whereas that of the amides could be easily completed with 40% sulphuric acid, dispensing with the previously known tedious

7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1310; 1928, 2070.

8. *Ibid.*, 1936, 1159.

9. Qudrat-i-Khuda, *this Journal*, 1931, 8, 277.

10. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1675.

11. *Annalen*, 1925, 445, 1; 1927, 453, 100, 103.

12. B. P. 425,885.

13. U.S.P. 2,265,184.

14. U.S.P. 2,183,357.

15. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 4407.

16. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1918, 93, 124.

1-anilinocycloheptane-1-cyanide on crystallisation from ethanol in colorless tiny needles had m.p. 90°; yield 9.3 g. (Found: C, 78.7; H, 8.7. $C_{14}H_{18}N_2$ requires C, 78.5; H, 8.5%).

Hydrochloride of 1-Anilinocycloheptane-1-isonitrile.—Evaporation of the ethanolic mother liquor provided an oily residue, strongly smelling of an isonitrile. This was dissolved in benzene and HCl gas passed through the solution, when a solid separated. It was filtered, washed with benzene, and dried; m.p. 215°.

1-Anilinocycloheptane-1-carboxylic Acid Amide.—The preceding cyanide (25 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc., cold, 18ml) in a conical flask (100 ml) and after keeping at room temperature for 48 hours, the contents were poured over crushed ice and made alkaline with strong ammonium hydroxide. The precipitated amide was filtered, washed, and dried; pure 1-anilinocycloheptane-1-carboxylic acid amide was crystallised in colorless shining flakes from ethanol, m.p. 142°, yield 27 g. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 8.6. $C_{14}H_{20}ON_2$ requires C, 72.4; H, 8.7%).

1-Anilinocycloheptane-1-carboxylic Acid.—The above acid amide (16.8 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc., 75ml) in a r.b. flask (500 ml); water (120 ml) was then cautiously added and the mixture refluxed on a sand bath for 4 hours. The contents were cooled, neutralised with strong ammonium hydroxide, and acidified with glacial acetic acid; the crude acid thus precipitated was filtered, washed, and dried. Pure 1-anilinocycloheptane-1-carboxylic acid on crystallisation from ethanol as clusters of colorless needles had m.p. 157-58°. [Found: C, 72.2; H, 8.0; equiv., 232.8. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2N$ requires C, 72.1; H, 8.2%; equiv., 233 (monobasic)].

1-Anilinocycloheptane-1-carbinol.— $LiAlH_4$ (1.9 g., 0.05M) was made into a slurry in dry ether (50 ml) and poured into a three-necked flask (500 ml) fitted with a stirrer, a separator funnel, and a Soxhlet which in turn carried a double walled water condenser. The preceding acid (4.6 g., 0.02M) was then placed in the Soxhlet which was continuously drawn into the reaction flask. The reaction product was worked up in the customary manner and pure 1-anilinocycloheptane-1-carbinol distilled at 207-208°/13mm as a colorless liquid. (Found: C, 76.9; H, 9.5. $C_{14}H_{21}ON$ requires C, 76.7; H, 9.7%).

Attempted Synthesis of Indoxyl Spiro-cycloheptane.—A mixture of 1-anilinocycloheptane-1-carboxylic acid (10 g.) and KOH (25 g.) was carefully heated in a nickel crucible to 340-50° and maintained thereabout for 30 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled, lixiviated with water in a pestle and mortar and, filtered. The residue on drying was then subjected to distillation under vacuum when no product was obtained.

Cycloheptanone (0.05M), dissolved in glacial acetic acid, was similarly condensed with *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-toluidines, α - and β -naphthylamines, *o*-anisidine, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines, *p*-bromoaniline, and *m*-nitroaniline (each 0.05M) in presence of aqueous potassium cyanide (0.05M). The products, 1-arylamino-cycloheptane-1-cyanides (a), obtained are shown in Table I. These nitriles on hydration furnished the corresponding amides (b) (Table I).

Attempted Synthesis of Indoxyl Spiro-cyclohexane.—1-Anilinocyclohexane-1-cyanide needed for the investigation was prepared from cyclohexanone (19.6g., 0.2M), aniline (18.6 g., 0.2M), and potassium cyanide (13 g., 0.2M) and had m.p. 76°. It was converted into its amide, m.p. 148°, and the corresponding acid, m.p. 142°.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Cryst. appearance.	Solvent.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1. 1- <i>p</i> -Te-1-cyanide (a)	Light yellow prisms	Benzene-light petroleum	72°	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₂	78.7	78.9	8.6	8.8
2. 1- <i>p</i> -Te-1-carboxylic acid amide (b)	Light brown plates	Benzene-ethanol	132°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ ON ₂	73.2	73.1	8.8	9.0
3. 1- <i>m</i> -Te-1-cyanide (a)	Brownish orange tiny needles	Benzene-light petroleum	78-70°	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₂	78.7	78.9	8.9	8.8
4. 1- <i>m</i> -Te-1-carboxylic acid amide (b)	Colorless triangular needles	Benzene-ethanol	133°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ ON ₂	73.2	73.1	9.1	9.0
5. 1- <i>o</i> -Te-1-cyanide (a)	Colorless needles	Light petroleum	76°	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₂	78.7	78.9	8.6	8.8
6. 1- <i>o</i> -Te-1-carboxylic acid amide (b)	Colorless tiny rectangular plates	Benzene-light petroleum	80°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ ON ₂	73.2	73.1	9.2	9.0
7. 1- α -Na-1-cyanide (a)	Light brown rectangular rods	Benzene	115-16°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂	81.0	81.8	7.6	7.6
8. 1- α -Na-1-carboxylic acid amide (b)	Brown needles	"	157°	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ ON ₂	76.4	76.6	7.9	7.9
9. 1- β -Na-1-cyanide (a)	Light brown tiny rods	"	105°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂	81.8	81.8	7.7	7.6
10. 1- β -Na-1-carboxylic acid amide (b)	Dark brown tiny prisms	"	156-57°	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ ON ₂	76.5	76.6	8.0	7.9
11. 1- <i>m</i> -No-1-cyanide (a)	Bright yellow triangular prisms	"	106-107°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	64.7	64.8	6.7	6.6
12. 1- <i>m</i> -No-1-carboxylic acid amide (b)	Orange-red rods	Ethanol-benzene	162-63°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	60.5	60.6	6.9	6.9
13. 1- <i>o</i> -Ac-1-cyanide (a)	White thin plates	Benzene	83°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ON ₂	73.5	73.7	8.3	8.2
14. 1- <i>m</i> -Ca-1-cyanide (a)	Shining white needles	Ethanol	72°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ Cl	Cl : 14.5%			14.2%
15. 1- <i>m</i> -Ca-carboxylic acid amide (b)	White needles	"	144°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ Cl	Cl : 13.1			13.3
16. 1- <i>p</i> -Ca-1-cyanide (a)	Thin white needles	"	85°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ Cl	Cl : 14.0			14.2
17. 1- <i>p</i> -Ca-1-carboxylic acid amide (b)	Thin plates	"	151°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ ON ₂ Cl	Cl : 13.5			13.3
18. 1- <i>p</i> -Ba-1-cyanide (a)	Thin needles	"	160°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ Br	Br : 27.6			27.3

Attempts to convert No. 13 and 18 into their amides were unsuccessful as sulphonation seemed to have taken place.

Te = Toluidinocycloheptane.

No = Naphthylaminocycloheptane.

No = Nitranilinocycloheptane.

Ac = Anisidinocycloheptane.

Ca = Chloroanilinocycloheptane.

Ba = Bromoanilinocycloheptane.

(a). To polyphosphoric acid, prepared from phosphorus pentoxide (50 g.) and syrupy phosphoric acid (20 ml), contained in a r.b. flask (250 ml), was added 1-anilinocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid (5 g.) and the contents were heated in an oil bath at 120°, 150°, 200°, and 250° separately for periods of 3 to 10 hours. At lower temperatures, the original product was recovered unchanged, but with the increase in temperature and duration of the reaction, tar formation took place. In experiments carried out at 150° and 200°, very small amounts of a liquid, b.p. 70°/8 mm, were obtained from the tar, but no indoxyl spiro-compound could be obtained. This had a tendency to undergo polymerisation and hence its identity could not be established.

(b). To 1-anilinocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid (5 g.), contained in a r.b. flask (100 ml), dry benzene (50 ml) and thionyl chloride (10 ml) were added and the contents refluxed for an hour. Excess of thionyl chloride and benzene were then removed; carbon disulphide (30 ml) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (10 g.) were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hours; the contents were stored overnight. After removing the solvent, the complex was broken up with ice-cold 15% aqueous NaOH (100 ml) and extracted with ether. After drying the ethereal solution and removing ether, a tarry product was left, which on distillation at 130°/10 mm afforded a colorless liquid. On keeping, it developed a dark colour and polymerised to a resinous mass and no indoxyl spiro-cyclohexane was obtained.

(c). An intimate mixture of 1-anilinocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid (5 g.) and soda-mide (10 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 150° and 200° separately for 5 hours. The reaction product on working up did not provide any indoxyl spiro-cyclohexane.

1-Anilinocyclohexane-1-carbinol.—1-Anilinocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid (4.3 g., 0.02M) was reduced with LiAlH_4 (1.9 g., 0.05M) in the usual manner and pure carbinol distilled at 176.78°/10 mm as a straw-coloured liquid. (Found: C, 75.9; H, 9.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}$ requires C, 76.1; H, 9.3%).